

Tungro (RTV) development in rice

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We studied the development of RTV infection in rice varieties with different levels of resistance to the vector green leafhopper (GLH). In a wet season trial Aug-Oct 1985, high infection by rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) was

28 DT, coincidental with detection of RTBV + RTSV. RTSV infection rate was highest about a month after transplanting, and decreased thereafter, whereas infection with RTBV + RTSV increased remarkably 1 mo after

1. Percentage of RTBV and RTSV infection assessed by latex test in 6 rice varieties at different times after transplanting, IRRI. WS = wet season, DS = dry season.

2. Percentage of RTBV and RTSV infection assessed by latex test, and RTV incidence based on symptoms in variety TN1 at different times after transplanting. IRRI, 1987 DS.

found 30 d after transplanting (DT) in all varieties except IR54 and IR58, which have GLH resistance. RTSV infection remained high to the end of the test period, except in susceptible TN1 and IR22. Infection with both RTSV and rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) was high in TN1 and IR22.

In a similar trial Jan-Mar (dry season) 1986, RTSV infection at 30 DT was low even in TN1 and IR22. Infection increased slowly with both viruses in all varieties. RTV development was more rapid in susceptible TN1 and IR22 than in moderately resistant IR36 and IR42. IR54 and IR58 had low infection, regardless of cropping season (Fig. 1).

In the Jan-Mar 1987 trial using TN1 plants, RTSV infection occurred as early as 14 DT. RTV symptoms appeared at

transplanting (Fig. 2).

The rate of RTV development varied among varieties and cropping seasons. RTSV infection could occur soon after transplanting, about a month before appearance of RTV symptoms. RTSV incidence also varied with cropping season. □

Stability of bacterial blight (BB) resistance in IR varieties

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Eleven IR varieties were evaluated for BB resistance at AanRen, Hunan, 1975-

87. Seedlings were transplanted in 1 row at 18- × 18-cm spacing. Plants were artificially inoculated (clipping method) with a virulent local isolate at maximum tillering. Disease reaction was recorded 20 d after inoculation.

IR22, IR26, IR32, IR36, IR38, and IR42 showed stable resistance, with a narrow reaction range. IR20, IR28, IR29, IR30, and IR34 had a wider reaction range (see table). □

Stability of BB resistance in IR varieties. Hunan, China.

Variety	Test duration	BB reaction ^a	
		Range	Average
IR20	1975-47	1-5	3.15
IR22	1975-87	1-3	2.85
IR26	1975-87	1-3	2.38
IR28	1975-87	1-5	3.30
IR29	1975-47	1-5	3.00
IR30	1975-87	1-5	3.46
IR32	1976-87	1-3	2.67
IR34	1976-47	1-5	3.16
IR36	1976-87	1-3	2.67
IR38	1976-87	1-3	2.67
IR42	1976-87	1-3	2.67

^aStandard evaluation system for rice.

Reaction of rice varieties with xa-5 to four Philippine races of bacterial blight (BB)

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More than 100 varieties having recessive gene xa-5 for BB resistance have been identified (genetic analysis using BB race 1). The xa-5 gene conveys resistance to BB races 1,2, and 3. We have found that varieties with xa-5 give widely variable reaction to race 4.

We reinoculated (clipping method) 6 plants each of 74 varieties with 4 races at maximum tillering. All varieties were resistant to races 1, 2, and 3 (see table). However, 52 were susceptible or moderately susceptible and 22 were resistant or moderately resistant to race 4.

We are analyzing some varieties resistant to race 4 to determine if they

Reaction of rice varieties with xa-5 to 4 Philippine races of BB.

Variety	IRRI acc. no.	Country of origin	Reaction ^a to races			
			1 (PXO 61)	2 (PXO 86)	3 (PXO 79)	4 (PXO 71)
Hashikalmi	3397	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
Kele	25881	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
Aus 25 1	29043	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Aus 449	29206	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Bageri	16193	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Dharial	3396	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
DV29	8816	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
DV319	8880	Bangladesh	R	R	R	R
DD100	8649	Bangladesh	MR	MR	MR	MS
DNJ 142	8426	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
DV32	8818	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
DV52	8828	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
DV85	8839	Bangladesh	R	R	R	R
DV86	8840	Bangladesh	R	R	R	R
DZ78	8555	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Pankhiraj	24139	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Dharial	34034	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MR
UCP 28	8728	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Laksmijota	31595	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Lahargura	25886	Bangladesh	R	R	R	MS
Loroi	27567	Bangladesh	R	R	R	R
Chinsurah Boro II	11484	India	R	R	R	R
Koalarata	28598	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC6231	12260	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC6565	20400	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7001	20436	India	MR	R	R	S
ARC7013	20437	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7043	20458	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7045	20460	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7046	20461	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7055	20468	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7060	20471	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7090	20490	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7098	20498	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC7102	20501	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7128	20524	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7207	20545	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7260	12346	India	R	R	R	S
ARC7291	12356	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7323	20602	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7336	20606	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7406	20617	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7416	20625	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC7423	20627	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC10027	20655	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC10376	20887	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC10520	20967	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC10952	12682	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC11067	42623	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11071	21184	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11072	21186	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC11075	21188	India	R	R	R	S
ARC11083	21189	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11092	21192	India	R	R	R	MS
ARC11109	21199	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11121	21207	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11204	21223	India	R	R	R	MR
ARC11219	21236	India	R	R	R	MR
BJI	3711	Nepal	R	R	R	R
Banglaluwa	16268	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Devarasi	16173	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Dudhi	16256	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Lal Ahu	16121	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Lalaka Gadur	16255	Nepal	R	R	R	S
Lal Sar	16185	Nepal	R	R	R	MS
Matury	16190	Nepal	R	R	R	S
Nakhi	16254	Nepal	R	R	R	S
Ram Bilash	16273	Nepal	R	R	R	MS

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